

THE CONTRIBUTION OF CHARLOTTE BRONTE TO ENGLISH LITERATURE

Qulliyeva Moxigul Maxmudovna

Termez State Pedagogical Institute

Faculty of Foreign language and literature (888089660).

3-course student e-mail: @MoxigulQulliyeva-fw1oc

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10143842>

Abstract. This article provides more information about Charlotte Bronte and her classic novel “Jane Eyre”. The role of the characters involved in the novel and their significance in Jane Eyre’s life is explained.

Key words: English literature, novel, feminist, Currer Bell, Charlotte Bronte, Jane Eyre, Ms. Reed lady, Mr. Rochester, Blanche Ingram, Helen Burns, Mr. Lloyd.

ВКЛАД ШАРЛОТТЫ БРОНТЕ В АНГЛИЙСКУЮ ЛИТЕРАТУРУ

Аннотация. В этой статье представлена дополнительная информация о Шарлотте Бронте и ее классическом романе «Джейн Эйр». Объясняется роль героев романа и их значение в жизни Джейн Эйр.

Ключевые слова: английская литература, роман, феминистка, Каррер Белл, Шарлотта Бронте, Джейн Эйр, мисс Рид-леди, мистер Рочестер, Блани Ингрэм, Хелен Бернс, мистер Ллойд.

Introduction: There are many writers and poets world literature. And all of them has made a great deal of contribution to English literature and has maintained its own place are writers who have many readers. Also Charlotte Bronte became famous one of the writers all over the world with her work “Jane Eyre”. Jane Eyre is one of the most important works of English literature.

Main part: Jane Eyre is a classic novel written by Charlotte Bronte and was first published in 1847 under the pen name “Currer Bell“. The novel is set in the early 19th century and is largely based on Bronte’s own experiences and observations. It is considered a significant work of feminist literature, as it challenges the traditional gender roles and expectation of the time. The story follows Jane Eyre, an orphaned young woman who grows up in the household of her cruel aunt and cousins. Novel has been adapted into numerous films television series and stage productions.

The novel begins with Jane Eyre as a young orphan living with her cruel aunt and cousins. Her aunt and cousins mistreated her since she was poor, dependent and an outsider. One day, after Jane fights with her cousin, Mrs. Reed punishes her by having her locked up in the Reed room, where her uncle. Once she recovers, She was eventually sent to Lowood school, where she face harsh conditions run by the greedy, hypocritical Mr. Brocklehurst. The school had terrible living condition and harsh discipline and Brocklehurst used the school’s funds to improve his family’s rich lifestyle than for the student and the building. But the school can be also finds friendship and education point for Jane.

While at Lowood, Jane knows a person who teaches her about personal prejudice and Christian beliefs. After a consumption outbreak occurs at the school, Helen dies and arrangements are made at Lowood to improve the building and its conditons. After living school, Jane accepts a job and becomes a governess at Thorfield Hall, where she fell in love with employer that a man

named Rochester. When Rochester begins to have affection for a richer woman, Jane is despondent, but, he turns her away. She knew that Mr. Rochester had already married and their relationship was ended by this revelation [1]. At first, Jane and Rochester's relationship is that of employee and employer. However, as time goes on Jane and Rochester both develop feelings for each other. Nevertheless, Mr. Rochester believes he must use jealousy to find out for certain if Jane has feelings for him. When Rochester's secret is revealed, Jane flees from him.

Mr. Rochester is one of the main characters in Charlotte Bronte's novel *Jane Eyre*. He is described as roughly forty years old. He has long dark hair, dark eyes and a brooding nature. In *Jane Eyre*, Mr. Rochester is described as not a handsome man. Despite not physically being the most attractive man, he is described as moody, dark and intense. However, he is very desired in society and is a great host. Also, Rochester is considered a Byronic hero. A Byronic hero is one who has several characteristics of intense moodiness, arrogance and mysterious. Additionally, a Byronic hero can have a troubled past or dark secret. Initially, Jane does not reject Rochester until she learns that Mr. Rochester is already married to a living woman. Despite the fact that Rochester believes he was tricked into the marriage and that his wife is not mentally stable, Jane refuses to become Rochester's mistress on principle, knowing that is all she could be since he is already married. Rochester develops love for Jane Eyre in the novel. However, he believes that Jane will not flout the conventions of the time and has to trick her into admitting her feelings for him[2].

Meanwhile, Mr. Rochester, until he had his power changes by one, usually had more command over different women he had meet over the years. Celine Varens and Blanche Ingram are examples in which Rochester first had an interest. They either did not return their affections or were already part of a higher social status, which meant they were not worthy of being with Rochester.

Both Jan and Mr. Rochester also have something in common, for they both had troubled pasts that had secrets that had been hidden until they were both discovered. In addition, another super natural event happened when Jane heard Rochester's voices calling for her on the moors, and his cries for her for help urged her to return to him. As such, Bronte had written Gothic elements to evaluate the novel's analysis of the Gothic genre. *Jane Eyre* is sometimes seen as a Gothic novel because the narrative elements expose the reader to fear and mystery. By the novel's ending, most sympathetic characters have married as equals, while the minor caring could not fit in. This includes Bertha Mason while she is already mentally unstable, she can not let Rochester have complete control over her and she ends up succumbing to her shallowness of being unequal.

English novelist noted for *Jane Eyre* a strong narrative of a women in conflict with her natural desires and social condition. The novel gave new truthfulness to Victorian fiction. She later wrote "*Shirley*" (1849) and "*Villette*" (1853). *Jane Eyre* was published during a time when Gender roles were defined differently from one another, mainly to women who were mostly described as being less dependent and commanded by men as they were more solid and confident than their female counterparts.

Throughout her journey, Jane Eyre strives to be more independent and mature after she was neglected in her childhood. Mr. Brocklehurst and Mrs. Reed see her as wicked when she explains how the Psalms are not interesting. She also expresses her opinion on the different

positions between men and women. She claims that women should be calmer and can show off their inner feelings and situations that they find themselves being put into by men[3].

In Jane Eyre novel, there are many other people besides Rochester who are important in Jane's life. They are Mrs. Reed lady and her children who are Jane's aunt and her cousins. From her youth and independence Jane made her journey with the morals of Christianity and spiritualism. As a child, she is shunned by the Reeds since she is seen as immoral and can not control her attitude and one servant even warns her of God's punishments the more she misbehaves. She even thought religion was not vital, especially when she stated that Psalms are not exciting and Brocklehurst and Reed lady think she is a wicked girl due to their hypocrisy in Christian belief.

It is not until Jane meets Helen Burns that she finally realizes how important religion is for growing up and being more moral in society. Helen often advises Jane to let God teach her stay true to her spiritualism, such as learning to love her enemies.

This is explained when Jane visits Mrs. Reed on her deathbed, she does not comfort her but instead forgives her for her actions and while her aunt never reconciled with her Jane believes she still at least did the right thing. Helen is also devoted to her religion even in death she hopes to find peace in Heaven. After her friend's help, Jane can also use her religious values with passion, such as someone she can share her commitment with but, not through marriage.

Critics often overlooked mid-19th-century novels written by woman as unimportant other than simply providing entertainment since most female novels were generally romance novels. It was also usually difficult for women to be novelist and have their books published, expect that publishers would likely take them seriously if they wrote under a male pen name. The three Bronte sisters used male pseudonyms when they became authors, mainly life that they used the pen names since they felt that their works would not be seen as feminine and would be looked down prejudice[4].

Conclusion: In conclusion, most of events in Jane Eyre were loosely based on Bronte's life. Jane has to live at her aunt's house after her parents's death. And because of her aunt and her cousins, her life is full of challenges. In spite of the fact that he met many good people. In the novel, per person is related to Jane's life.

REFERENCES

1. "Jane Eyre" IMDb ,www.imdb.com.
2. www.study.com Mr. Rochester in Jane Eyre
3. www.refseek.com Jane Eyre classic Liturature
4. www.Science.gov.